

Comparative Analysis of Requirements Elicitation Techniques used in Software Industry in Sri Lanka

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Abstract

This study examines the requirements elicitation techniques practiced in the Sri Lankan software industry and analyzes their associated benefits and challenges, highlighting the critical importance of effective elicitation in software development, where unclear or incomplete requirements can lead to costly rework, delays, or project failure. A qualitative research approach was adopted, using semi-structured interviews with business analysts from software companies in the Colombo district, representing the broader Sri Lankan software sector. The collected data were analyzed using thematic analysis to identify recurring patterns and key insights. The findings indicate that a variety of elicitation techniques, including interviews, document analysis, workshops, brainstorming, prototyping, and observation, are widely applied in practice. While many of these techniques align with internationally recognized standards, certain practices, particularly document analysis and change request handling, demonstrate contextual adaptations influenced by organizational culture, stakeholder behavior, and project environments. The results further reveal that each elicitation technique presents distinct strengths and limitations, confirming that no single method is universally effective and that appropriate selection depends on project characteristics, stakeholder needs, communication settings, and organizational processes. The study also highlights that accurate, structured, and context-aware elicitation significantly contributes to project success by improving clarity, reducing misunderstandings, and ensuring a shared understanding of user requirements. This study explores real-world requirements elicitation in a developing country, offering practical and theoretical insights. Despite limited generalizability, it recommends future research on AI-supported tools and mixed-method approaches for broader validation.

Keywords: *Requirements Elicitation, Elicitation Techniques, Comparative Analysis, Software Industry*